

EVALUATING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF LIQUID FERTILIZER PRODUCED FROM BANANA PEELS ON SOIL NOURISHMENT OF A PHOSPHATE-DEFICIENT CORN LEAVE

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Abstract: *This research work, evaluates the effectiveness of liquid fertilizer produced from banana peels on soil nourishment of a phosphate-deficient corn leave. Thus, liquid fertilizer produced from banana peels through extraction by submersion for immersion was applied to soil habituating corn leave cultivation, identified to be deficient in phosphate nutrients, to evaluate the effectiveness of the solution in providing required mineral nutrients for the remediation of the soil environment used by plants. It was found that the corn leaves responded to the application of the fertilizer produced within three to four weeks, signifying the positive effect on recovery upon intake of phosphorus nutrients.*

Keywords: *Liquid Fertilizers; Banana; Corn Leave; Soil - Crop Nutrient; Phosphate Deficiency; Fertilizer Production; Soil Nourishment; etc.*

I. INTRODUCTION

In many third-world nations, agriculture is the main source of income for the population [3]. It is widely documented that optimal crop production can only be achieved by providing plants with the sixteen nutrients - both macro- and micronutrients - that they require [13;12]. These nutrients are expected to be made available to crops from produced fertilizers which supplements for natural nutrients. The liquid fertilizers provide the traditional macro and micronutrients for crop production thereby enhancing agricultural production. Both macro- and micronutrients can be turned into nanoscale fertilizers, but nano-phosphorus (NP) and nano-nitrogen (NN) fertilizers will be

particularly useful due to the significant demand for these nutrients among vegetable crops [12]. Liquid fertilizers provide advantageous functions like: improvement of flowering rate, fruiting rate, promote fruit expansion as well as make fruit colour more beautiful, prolongment of life - span of plants, increase yield to about 15 to 30 percent, protect plant nutrient balance and promote the healthy growth of plants. Reduced agricultural productivity, nutritional scarcity, and climate change are some of the biggest challenges agricultural scientists face today [12]. Consequently, it is believed that current agricultural outputs need to be increased by as much as 50–70% to fulfill both present and future food requirements [16]. The need for the conservation of the environment as well as proper management of natural resources is vital for future sustenance [8]. The knowledge of natural extraction process of bioproducts are of great importance to Bioresource Engineering application in soil nutrient improvement. Soil and water engineers, soil scientists, agriculturists *etc.*, have deployed this medium in natural remediation of soil using a chemical toxic free fertilizer.

Liquid Fertilizer: Farmers have been using commercial fertilizers extensively for the last 50 years, which contain a balanced distribution of the three main essential nutrients needed for optimum plant growth: nitrogen, phosphorous, and potassium. Liquid fertilizer has potential of replacing the traditional chemical fertilizer and it significantly improves the soil nutrient content [18]. The application of liquid fertilizers directly to the leaf surface by using spraying method is known as foliar application. The leaves can easily and directly absorb the nutrients through their stomata openings and also through the epidermis [15]. The raw materials of a bio - product are processed through appropriate procedures to produce a liquid fertilizer. Liquid fertilizer of various kinds depending on source have been made in the past by experts. Example is the seaweed liquid fertilizer. According to [11], after processed by physical crushing, high temperature extraction and other nutrient compounding, the seaweed is finally made to liquid seaweed fertilizer. The liquid seaweed fertilizer has all kinds of nutritional ingredient and active ingredient of seaweed including alginate, mannitol, Iodine, amino acid, alginate polysaccharide, carbohydrate, vitamins, CTK, mineral materials, micronutrients, *etc.*, [11]. In a similar vein, liquid fertilizers from various bioproducts are produced with the intent of nutrient availability. Liquid fertilizers can be recovered from digestate by techniques such as pressurized membrane filtration, ammonia stripping, evaporation, forward osmosis, electrodialysis, and phosphorus precipitation by struvite, [18]. Phosphorus provides energy in the form of ATP and NADPH for plant metabolism (photosynthesis and respiration); additionally, it is a component of DNA, RNA, nucleotides, and cell membranes [1].

Banana: The scientific name for banana is *Musa*, from the Musaceae family of flowering tropical plants, which distinctively showcases the banana fruit clustered at the top of the plant [3]. *Musa* are believed to have originated in Southeast Asia but their introduction into Africa is unclear [4]. Banana cultivation requires a certain amount of fertilizer application to boost nutrient

availability. Fertilizer requirements are 200 to 400 kg/ha N, 45 to 60 kg/ha P, and 240 to 480 kg/ha K per year [2]. The ripening process will change the peel from being thick and stiff to thin and more flexible, with brown spots surfacing until the entire peel darkens [3]. Banana peels contain plant chemicals in the form of antioxidants and have long been used in traditional and folk medicine as an antiseptic and anti-inflammatory to promote wound healing such as for bug bites, minor burns, and sunburns. This chemical substance from the peel is applied to Injuries to fasten healing. The inside of the banana peel is pressed on a wound for several minutes [23], for its medicinal functions. With the above-mentioned advantages and more, there exist some disadvantages of the peels. Disposal of these peels (pomace) may cause environmental problems [23]. A typical banana in its cultivation can be seen in Figure 1 (1) below;

Figure 1: The Development of Banana [2]

The optimization of banana processing has been studied to reduce the production of the waste (annual rejection is about 1/4 of the banana fruit) and to improve the bioavailability and utilization of nutrients available in this fruit, highlighting the use of green banana (GB) products [22;19]. Edible bananas are seedless due to either sterility or parthenocarpy and are derived from these species in various combinations such as East African highlands bananas and dessert bananas (AAA), cooking bananas (ABB, AA), and plantains (AAB) [5].

Corn Leave: Corn (*Zea mays* L.) is otherwise known as maize plant. The two basic methods for corn leaf staging that are used in the field today are the leaf collar method and the droopy leaf method. In this research work, the leaf collar method was deployed. This method determines leaf stage in corn by counting the number of leaves on a plant with visible leaf collars, beginning with the lowermost, short, rounded-tip true leaf and ending with the uppermost leaf with a visible leaf collar [20]. In the droopy leaf method, leaf staging also begins with the short first leaf. [20] noted that leaf counting then differs, though, by ending not with the uppermost leaf with a visible collar, but at that leaf that is at least 40 to 50 percent exposed from the whorl.

Plant Nutrient Deficiency: Nutrient deficiency refers to the inadequacy in the plant necessary nutritional requirements. Healthy plant growth and reproduction requires 17 nutrients [21]. This includes the basic nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium that makes up the NPK found in fertilizers. Macronutrients like the Nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, calcium, sulphur, and magnesium are very essential for plants in large quantities. Micronutrients, also known as trace or minor elements like the copper, manganese, boron, iron, zinc, and molybdenum are essential at little quantities. According to [7], nutrient deficiency may occur due to one or more of the following reasons: The soil or growth medium is deficient in the required nutrient; The soil is not sufficiently moist to allow the roots to take up and transport the nutrients; The soil is not deficient in the nutrient, but another factor limits the plant's nutrient uptake ability (some nutrients, for example, are more available to the plant at certain pH levels); The nutrient is unable to reach the organ where it is needed most (example is blossom end rot of tomato, pepper, and eggplant); A too - high concentration of one nutrient may outcompete the uptake of a similar nutrient (example, calcium uptake can be suppressed by the presence of excess potassium, sodium or magnesium). The determining factors for a conclusive decision making on the type of nutrient need by a plant as well as symptoms of deficiency of these nutrients are presented in figure two (2) below;

Figure 2: Visual Assessment Flow Chart for Cl, K, Mg, Mo, N, P Nutrients [6]

Nutrient deficiency symptoms include complete crop failure at the seedling stage, appearance of specific leaf symptoms, severe stunting of plants, internal abnormalities like clogging of conductive tissues, yield differences, delayed or abnormal maturity, reduction in quality of crops like reduced oil, protein or starch content, and storage quality [14]. [7] recommended corrective measures for phosphate nutrient deficiency to include: Ensuring the area has adequate drainage, use of soil amendment such as lime to adjust pH, tilling or plowing the soil, and fertilization using bone meal, rock phosphate, ammonium phosphate or manure.

II. MATERIALS

The main material used is the study area, located at the department of Agricultural Engineering, in Delta State University of Science and Technology, Ozoro. This provided the ground base for the actualization of this research work. The location is presented in figure three (3) below;

Figure 3: Map And Location of The Study Area (Delta State University of Science and Technology, DSUST) In Ozoro and Its Location in Map of Nigeria [10]

The sub - study areas are: the soil and water engineering laboratory where extraction was carried out, and the research demonstration site of the department where testing and evaluation of the laboratory produced were obtained. Other materials include: Banana peels, Water solution, Water tank, Knapsack Sprayer, Cultivated corn plant, etc.

III. METHODOLOGY

Nutrient Deficiency Identification Identification of plant nutrient deficiency was obtained using tissue visual indicator presented in figure two (2) above. Moreover, this identification utilized the recommendation of [21] which points that the first step to visual identification of a nutrient deficiency is to determine where on the plant the symptoms are appearing.

Liquid Fertilizer Production 20 kg weighted banana fruit peels were immersed in the 1000ml laboratory cylindrical containers for three (3) days. During which the nutrients were naturally extracted into the water solution, which was introduced on the corn cultivation (identified to be

lacking phosphorus nutrients as the corn leaves possesses purple colour at the side edges of the leaves). The water to peels ratio was considered, the rate of recovery, and the nutrient extract decoded by the solute colour during the immersion period.

Liquid Fertilizer Application The produce was applied on plant root at 100 ml on daily bases for two weeks. In evaluating the effectiveness of the produced fertilizer on the corn leave, field inspection using the leaf collar method, was deployed in monitoring the difference in growth stage of corn leave under the influence of fertilizer and that of natural nutrient. Test for acid level variation was obtained upon solution application.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The results obtained from the course of this experimental study are presented below;

The result from extract process is presented in figure four (4) below;

Figure 4: Nutrient extract from banana peels in solution

The nutrient extract is decoded in the colouring. This took effect from the day two (2) of the experiment. The solution with the extracted nutrients is emptied to a storage container for use. The results obtained from field applications and inspection are presented in table one (1) below;

Table 1: Result Obtained from Produced Fertilizer Application

Exp. No.	Leave Stage, V	Acidic Neutralization effect	Fertilizer Impact on Recovery
1	2	- 0.7	High
2	3	- 6	High
3	3	- 1.1	High
Av.	3	0.8	High

Phosphorus deficient leaves were characterized with narrow and a bluish tint, with tips of the upper leaves turning purple. Plant was also becoming stunted. Other nutrient attributed deficiency abounds, for example nitrogen. Nitrogen deficiency result to overall plant color of a pale green, plant becoming stunted, yellowing of lower leaves in a V pattern from the tip backward and leaves may turn completely brown and die. Potassium (K) deficiency includes lower leaves becoming yellow from the tip, plant becoming stunted, while leaf edges turn brown. The need for food compositional characteristics is a requisite for choosing appropriate food substances for required purpose [8]. For the nutrient extraction purpose, the three macro nutrients (NPK) were obtained though the phosphate was of more significant to this work. Nitrogen is one of the main elements in protein, Nitrogen is also a component of nucleic acid, DNA, RNA, genes, chromosomes, enzymes, chlorophyll, secondary metabolites (alkaloids), and amino acids; Nitrogen accounts for about 1 to 6 % of plant dry matter, depending on the species [1]. Potassium being a major nutrient in fertilizers also has its contribution in soil - crop nutrient functions. Potassium is important for movement of sugars, starch formation, pH stabilization, drought tolerance, cell turgor, enzyme activation, and regulation of stomata opening and closing [1]. The H₂O content in the solution helped in reducing the acidic level by 0.8, thus, serves as a good source of acid level neutralizer. Liquid fertilizers from banana peels have low acid levels, acidic pH as well as high protein. They cause increase in concentration of ammonia prior protein content.

V. CONCLUSION

From results obtained in this experiments, the liquid fertilizer produced from banana peels proved efficient in plant recovery from nutrient deficiency. It was thus concluded that, it is an efficient soil

remediation approach in soil engineering. Liquid fertilizer produced from banana peels is a bioresource produce for soil nourishment and remediation for nutrient and acidic imbalance.

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